

Elche, Spain Synagogue

also known as "Synagogue of Elche, Spain", "Basilica of Elche, Spain"

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**Supervised Entry, prepared from a literature review by a student or students under the direction of a Supervisor, typically as a classroom project; edited and vetted by Supervisor.*

Entry tags: Basilica, Synagogue, Temple, Religious Place

Archaeological structure unearthed by Nazi researchers. Traditionally celebrated as an early Christian basilica, recent research has unveiled that this structure probably functioned as a synagogue at some point in its history.

Date Range: 250 CE - 350 CE

Region: La Alcudia, Spain

Region tags: Spain

The site of Ancient Ilici, in La Alcudia, Spain, adjacent to modern day Elche, Spain.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The first excavations of the site were carried out by Pedro Ibarra y Ruiz and Eugene Albertini. Ibarra held a top position at a local museum and Albertini was an established professor. The next excavations of the site were carried out by Ramos Folques an amateur archaeologist who had "no apparent academic training." He was supervised by the German Reich during his excavations.

Reference: Robyn Walsh Faith. Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche Spain. *Jewish Studies Quarterly*, 23(2) doi: 10.1628/094457016X14781655923274.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: The first excavation by Pedro Ibarra y Ruiz and Eugene Albertini took place in

July/August 1905.

Reference: Robyn Walsh Faith. Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche Spain. *Jewish Studies Quarterly*, 23(2) doi: 10.1628/094457016X14781655923274.

– Year range: The second excavation by Ramon Folques supervised by Helmut Schlunk in 1948.

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: 14 km from Panta de Ponent 15.3 km from Panta de Llevant 21.5 km from the Alboran/Balearic Sea

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Architectural method, elevation levels, and materials seem to suggest that the rectangular structure of the Elche synagogue was built prior to the apsidal structure which was probably added at a later date. If this is correct, then it would make sense that the apse was added to convert the structure from an earlier Jewish synaoguge to a later Christian basilica.

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↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: Currently, the Elche Synagogue/Basilica is located within La Alcudia Archaeological Park. The park features excavations of neighboring parts of Ancient Ilici.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Social

– Sacrificial

Notes: It is possible that some sort of sacrifices were conducted at the site if it functioned as an early synagogue.

– Social

– Memorial

– Political

Notes: Politics seeped into early synagogue discourse and relations.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most likely the synagogue and basilica were finished in both instances and the current remains are simply what has withstood the test of time.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: At some point after the original excavation of the site, the masonry of the building was reset and the grounds were manicured for publicity purposes.

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: Architectural method, elevation levels, and materials seem to suggest that the rectangular structure of the Elche synagogue was built prior to the apsidal structure. If this is correct, then it would make sense that the apse was added to convert the structure from an earlier Jewish synagogue to a later Christian basilica.

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↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Presumably the reconstruction took place in the mid 20th century, perhaps the late 1930s or the 1940s.

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Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Yahweh and Jesus/Yahweh

Notes: When the structure functioned as a synagogue, it was most likely dedicated to Yahweh, the Jewish supreme god. If the structure functioned as a Christian church at another point in its history, then it was probably dedicated to Jesus and/or Yahweh depending on the theology of the parishioners. It is not clear whether worship practices are currently taking place at the site given its designation as part of an archaeological park and its extremely degraded condition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: If this structure functioned as a synagogue and a church at different times in history, it could be argued that it was dedicated at one time to the Jewish supreme god Yahweh, and at another time to Jesus, or perhaps to both Jesus and Yahweh, or even Jesus-Yahweh depending on the Christian theology of the group that worshipped there.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Assuming that the structure functioned as a Christian basilica at some point in its history based on the apse, it was probable that Jesus was worshipped at this site. Depending on the point at which this site became a Church and the theology of the Christian worshippers, Jesus may have been understood as semi-divine.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: It would be more accurate to argue that Judaism promotes the veneration of prominent ancestors, as opposed to ancestor-worship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There's no evidence to suggest that the structure was commissioned or built by an official political entity. If it was first built as a synagogue, it was likely organized and built by a community of Jewish individuals for the purposes of diaspora worship and gathering.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest that this site was built for any purposes other than worship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the creation of the place sponsored by external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Churches and synagogues are typically not built with the explicit intention of a tangible reward being granted from Yahweh or Jesus. However, it is arguable that both Jews and Christians view the construction of a sacred space and the subsequent worship inside of those spaces

as favorable to their respective supreme being, and thus implicitly expect positive reinforcement of some variety if not on Earth, then in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 250 CE - 300 CE

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Transcriptions of the Torah and later the New Testament.

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Traditionally in synagogues the Torah (also known as the Jewish scriptures, the Hebrew Bible, and the Old Testament) was kept in a closed ark, except when used during worship, to mimic the sacred Ark of the Covenant that housed the stone tablets said to be received from Moses at Mount Sinai. The Ark of the Covenant is referenced repeatedly in the Torah. It is not known whether the New Testament was housed in a special location in early churches.

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest that Jewish or Christian worship is still practiced at the structure.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The apsidal structure in which the Elche Synagogue/Church existed appears to have been initially a rectangular structure to which an apse was later added. The evidence that points to this conclusion includes the fact that there is a large mosaic that only extends to the confines of the rectangular structure the apsidal structure is in much better shape preservation-wise than the rectangular structure, the apsidal structure is at a lower elevation than the rectangular structure, and the masonry techniques for the rectangular structure and apsidal structure are different.

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↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There is a mosaic across the floor of the rectangular portion of the apsidal structure.

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↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There is a mosaic across the floor of the rectangular portion of the apsidal structure.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: There is a small figurative scene of a sea voyage in poor condition.

Reference: Robyn Walsh Faith. Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche Spain. *Jewish Studies Quarterly*, 23(2) doi: 10.1628/094457016X14781655923274.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Reference: Robyn Walsh Faith. Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche Spain. *Jewish Studies Quarterly*, 23(2) doi: 10.1628/094457016X14781655923274.

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There are several text inscriptions in Greek including: "Vow of Archons and Elders" "Place of Prayer of the People" and "Good Voyage"

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↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Important non-figural decoration that may contribute to the structure's interpretation as a Jewish diaspora synagogue:

Notes: There is a seven branched candelabra within the mosaic which is likely a menorah, a classic iconographic symbol of Judaism. There is also a oval shaped decorative element near one of the Greek inscriptions which some argue could be an etrog, a fruit associated with Jewish religious traditions.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: Mention of the seven branched candelabra decoration was excluded from early archaeological writing on the structure and mosaic. The candelabra is damaged but clearly visible in the structure's mosaic.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: There are no statues present in the structure currently but it is possible that statues existed in the structure when it functioned as a site of worship.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief—as opposed to sculpture carved on the round—is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a small badly damaged figural representation of a sea voyage.

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a small badly damaged figural representation of a sea voyage.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: There are several text inscriptions in Greek including: "Vow of Archons and Elders" "Place of Prayer of the People" and "Good Voyage"

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: There is a seven branched candelabra within the mosaic which is likely a menorah, a classic iconographic symbol of Judaism. There is also a oval shaped decorative element near one of the Greek inscriptions which some argue could be an etrog, a fruit associated with Jewish religious traditions.

Reference: Robyn Walsh Faith. Reconsidering the Synagogue/Basilica of Elche Spain. *Jewish Studies Quarterly*, 23(2) doi: 10.1628/094457016X14781655923274.

Reference: Rachel Hachili. *The Menorah*. Boston: Brill. isbn: 978-90-04-37502-4.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural being (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what the small figurative decoration of a sea voyage within the floor mosaic connotes.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: There is a small, badly damaged figurative decoration of a sea voyage in one area of the floor mosaic.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what the small figurative decoration of a sea voyage within the floor mosaic connotes.

↳ Human narratives

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear what the small figurative decoration of a sea voyage within the floor mosaic connotes.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a seven branched candelabra within the mosaic which is likely a menorah, a classic iconographic symbol of Judaism. There is also a oval shaped decorative element near one of the Greek inscriptions which some argue could be an etrog, a fruit associated with Jewish religious traditions.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: While ancestor veneration is a prominent feature of Judaism, the veneration does not quite match the forthright practice of ancestor worship found in other religions. With regard to Christianity, it is arguable that worship of Jesus of Nazareth, an individual who according to Christian doctrine physically died and then was resurrected three days later, is in some sense worship of the dead. However, Christian theology does not promote necromancy and many people would likely argue against this understanding of Christian worship.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Yahweh, the Jewish supreme god is often described in anthropomorphic terms. For instance, Exodus 6:6 reads, "Say therefore to the Israelites, 'I am the Lord, and I will free you from the burdens of the Egyptians and deliver you from slavery to them. I will redeem you with an outstretched arm and with mighty acts of judgment.'" In a sense, Yahweh is also considered the supreme being in Christianity. Jesus is in a sense anthropomorphic but also understood as

literally human, which is somewhat different.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Notes: Yahweh and Jesus are best understood as supreme beings whose powers are omnipotent and thus extend beyond specific realms. However, although Yahweh and Jesus deal with chthonic issues, they are more commonly associated with Heaven which is often conceptualized as "above" as opposed to the "under-world."

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Notes: Yahweh and Jesus are best understood as supreme beings whose powers are omnipotent and thus extend beyond specific realms. However, although Yahweh and Jesus deal with chthonic issues, they are more commonly associated with Heaven which is often conceptualized as "above" as opposed to the "under-world."

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While Yahweh and Jesus are often referred to using royal discourse, there were also human kings of the nation of Israel that were not perceived of as divine. For more information see below: 1 Samuel 8:4-7 4 Then all the elders of Israel gathered together and came to Samuel at Ramah, 5 and said to him, "You are old and your sons do not follow in your ways; appoint for us, then, a king to govern us, like other nations." 6 But the thing displeased Samuel when they said, "Give us a king to govern us." Samuel prayed to the Lord, 7 and the Lord said to Samuel, "Listen to the voice of the people in all that they say to you; for they have not rejected you, but they have rejected me from being king over them. 2 Kings 19:15 And Hezekiah prayed before the Lord, and said: "O Lord the God of Israel, who are enthroned above the cherubim, you are God, you alone, of all the kingdoms of the earth; you have made heaven and earth. Revelation 11:15 Then the seventh angel blew his trumpet, and there were loud voices in heaven, saying, "The kingdom of the world has become the kingdom of our Lord and of his Messiah, and he will reign forever and ever." Luke 19:37-38 37 As he was now approaching the path down from the Mount of Olives, the whole multitude of the disciples began to praise God joyfully with a loud voice for all the deeds of power that they had seen, 38 saying, "Blessed is the king who comes in the name of the Lord! Peace in heaven, and glory in the highest heaven!"

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While Yahweh and Jesus are often referred to using royal discourse, there were also human kings of the nation of Israel that were not perceived of as divine. For more information see below: 1 Samuel 8:4-7 4 Then all the elders of Israel gathered together and came to Samuel at Ramah, 5 and said to him, "You are old and your sons do not follow in your ways; appoint for us, then, a king to govern us, like other nations." 6 But the thing displeased Samuel when they said, "Give us a king to govern us." Samuel prayed to the Lord, 7 and the Lord said to Samuel, "Listen to the voice of the people in all that they say to you; for they have not rejected you, but they have rejected me from being king over them. 2 Kings 19:15 And Hezekiah prayed before the Lord, and said: "O Lord the God of Israel, who are enthroned above the cherubim, you are

God, you alone, of all the kingdoms of the earth; you have made heaven and earth. Revelation 11:15 Then the seventh angel blew his trumpet, and there were loud voices in heaven, saying, "The kingdom of the world has become the kingdom of our Lord and of his Messiah, and he will reign forever and ever." Luke 19:37-38 37 As he was now approaching the path down from the Mount of Olives, the whole multitude of the disciples began to praise God joyfully with a loud voice for all the deeds of power that they had seen, 38 saying, "Blessed is the king who comes in the name of the Lord! Peace in heaven, and glory in the highest heaven!"

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: With reference to Jesus, Jesus is understood as being sort of related to the human monastic line of King David. For more information see below: Matthew 1:1-16 1 An account of the genealogy[a] of Jesus the Messiah,[b] the son of David, the son of Abraham. 2 Abraham was the father of Isaac, and Isaac the father of Jacob, and Jacob the father of Judah and his brothers,... 15 and Eliud the father of Eleazar, and Eleazar the father of Matthan, and Matthan the father of Jacob, 16 and Jacob the father of Joseph the husband of Mary, of whom Jesus was born, who is called the Messiah.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: 2 Chronicles 19:7 Now, let the fear of the Lord be upon you; take care what you do, for there is no perversion of justice with the Lord our God, or partiality, or taking of bribes. Isaiah 5:16 But the Lord of hosts is exalted by justice, and the Holy God shows himself holy by righteousness. Isaiah 30:18 Therefore the Lord waits to be gracious to you; therefore he will rise up to show mercy to you. For the Lord is a God of justice; blessed are all those who wait for him. Mark 10:18 Jesus said to him, "Why do you call me good? No one is good but God alone. Romans 12:2 Do not be conformed to this world, but be transformed by the renewing of your minds, so that you may discern what is the will of God—what is good and acceptable and perfect.

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the structure operated as a church, the church's members could have understood Jesus's presence to dwell in the structure. Depending on the theology of the church members, Jesus may have been perceived as formerly human.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Dependent upon the theology of either the Jews or early Christians that worshipped at this structure, it is possible that they understood Yahweh or Jesus to dwell in this structure to some extent.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If this structure functioned as a church at some point, it is possible that worshippers participated in the practice of "speaking in tongues" which indicates a union with the Holy Spirit, one of the three members of the Christian Trinity (The Father, The Son, & The Holy Spirit).

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the structure operated as a church, the church's members could have understood Jesus's presence to dwell in the structure. Depending on the theology of the church members, Jesus may have been perceived as both human and divine.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If this structure functioned as a church at some point, it is possible that worshippers participated in the practice of "speaking in tongues" which indicates a union with the Holy Spirit, one of the three members of the Christian Trinity (The Father, The Son, & The Holy Spirit). Jesus, who may have been understood as both human and divine, is considered a part of the trinity.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it's possible that statues or art forms did exist in some capacity during this structure's existence as either a synagogue or a church, it is unlikely that the structure was centered around a single cultic statue that was worshipped.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– No

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Traditionally in cultic Judaism various animal sacrifices were offered. It is unclear whether or not any time of animal sacrificing continued in early synagogues. It is unlikely that sacrifice was practiced by worshippers when the structure functioned as a church.

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are certainly references to sexuality and sexual behavior in the Hebrew Bible (aka the Old Testament) and the New Testament, more specifically Paul's writings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were laws concerning maintenance of the Jewish temple in Jerusalem, but it is unclear whether or not or to what extent those laws extended to synagogues in the diaspora. There is no indication that early churches were to be maintained in a specific manner.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Prayer was typical in both Jewish synagogues and early Christian churches and thus practitioners of both traditions probably participated in this form of communication with their respective god.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the structure functioned as a church at some point, depending upon the theology of the worshippers, they may have worshipped other important figures in Christianity such as saints.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although keeping the sabbath is mandated in the Hebrew Bible, it is unclear to what extent this was actually enforced in Jewish diaspora communities and early Christian communities.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably there was some sort of maintenance of the structure while it was functioning but in what manner and to what extent is unclear.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Meals did take place in early synagogues and churches but whether or not these meals qualified as feasts is debatable.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is possible that the structure in Elche could have functioned as a center for Jewish or Christian festivals during its existence as a synagogue and/or church, there is no indication that this was the case.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that some sort of divination practices took place at the structure in the context of it being a synagogue or church however there is no indication that this was the case.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that some sort of healing practices took place at the structure in the context of it being a synagogue or church however there is no indication that this was the case.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that doctrine at diaspora synagogues and early churches was periodically reviewed and corrected by a central authority but there is no definitive indication that this was the case at the Elche Synagogue/Church.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that practice and ritual at diaspora synagogues and early churches was periodically reviewed and corrected by a central authority but there is no definitive indication that this was the case at the Elche Synagogue/Church.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Local religious teachers known as Rabbis tended to be in charge of worship and study of the Hebrew Bible.

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear to what extent early church leaders devoted themselves to the church.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender

– Yes

Notes: While women played integral roles in both diaspora Judaism and early Christianity, religious specialists and leaders tended to be men.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity

– No

Notes: While Israelite priests had to descend from a certain tribal lineage, there is no indication that rabbis of diaspora synagogues had to prove any sort of background aside from Judaism. Early Christians were of diverse backgrounds and there is no indication that any ethnicity specifications were necessary to be a church leader.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no definitive indication that rabbis of diaspora synagogues or early church leaders had to be members of the upper echelons of society, although it is possible that many were simply for the reason that they had the resources to not work and devote themselves to religious matters.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicate to the place for life

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Hierarchies in diaspora synagogues are not well understood. For more information on early church organization, see: Philippians 1:1-3 1 Timothy 3:1-3 1 Timothy 3:8-13 Titus 1:7

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this palce used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably diaspora synagogues and early churches were used to educate future rabbis and church leaders about the Hebrew Bible and New Testament as well as rituals and traditions.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that in diaspora Jewish communities that synagogues and rabbis played a central role in community leadership including parceling out economic resources to some extent. There is indication that early Christians lived communally and thus it is possible that early Churches controlled economic resources to some extent as well.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage

– Field doesn't know

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.)

– No

↳ Function for water management

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network

– No

Writing/Scriptures

